

2,6-Dinitro-4-methylphenylhydrazine and its Condensation Products

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In extension to the work on the synthesis of polynitrophenylhydrazines and their derivatives¹⁻², 2,6-dinitro-4-methylphenylhydrazine has been obtained by the action of hydrazine hydrate on 1-chloro-2,6-dinitro-4-methylbenzene. The hydrazones have been prepared in the usual way. Structures of all these compounds follow from their methods of preparation.

2,6-Dinitro-4-methylphenylhydrazine.—1-Chloro-2,6-dinitro-4-methylbenzene (0.1M), dissolved in excess of ethanol, was treated dropwise with hydrazine hydrate (80%, 0.2M) at the room temperature. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water bath for a few min., concentrated, and cooled. The crude 2,6-dinitro-4-methylphenylhydrazine, thus obtained, was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol in shining orange-red needles, m.p. 110°, yield 60%. (Found: N, 26.48. C₇H₈O₄N₄ requires N, 26.41%).

Phenylhydrazones were obtained generally in quantitative yields by boiling a mixture of the hydrazine (0.5 g.) in ethanol (10 ml) and the carbonyl compound in equimolecular proportions in presence of H₂SO₄ (conc., 1 or 2 drops). On cooling, crystals of phenylhydrazone separated. These were recrystallised from ethyl acetate. Most of the hydrazones have sharp melting points. Their colour varies from orange-red to dark red. The melting points and analytical data of the hydrazones prepared are described in Table I.

TABLE I

Carbonyl compound.	M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Reqd.
Dibenzyl ketone	210°	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₄	13.91	13.86
Phenyl ethyl "	150°	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₄	17.12	17.07
<i>n</i> -Hexyl methyl "	216°	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₄	13.43	13.30
<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde	235°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₄ Cl	16.65	16.74
<i>p</i> -Hydroxy- "	254°	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₅ N ₄	17.79	17.72
<i>m</i> -Hydroxy- "	230°	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₅ N ₄	17.70	17.72
<i>p</i> -Bromoacetophenone	206°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₄ Br	14.28	14.25
<i>o</i> -Hydroxy- "	155°	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₅ N ₄	16.91	16.97
Cyclopentanone	120°	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₄	20.17	20.14

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1. Joshi and Deorha, *this Journal*, 1951, **28**, 34; 1957, **34**, 14.

2. Kapil and Joshi, *ibid.*, 1959, **36**, 417.